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IMPACT OF COLOR ON TODDLER'S EMOTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Color is an indispensable part of everyone's life. It holds the essence of excitement in it. From the very beginning till the end, our life revolves around color. Day and night baby to old

It is widely seen that color affects human behavior, especially children, as they sink into the environment very easily. Color can have both positive and negative influences on a toddler's life. Further expanding from the above points, we can have a look at toddlers' lives and how color affects them. Kids aged between 1 to 3 years are considered toddlers. An age where they are introduced to new environments, where they are exposed to new colors, shapes, patterns, and textures. Keenly observing their daily activities we can conclude that how the elements in their surroundings reflect on their emotions. Toddlers are playful in nature and have strong reflexes leading to responding faster towards bright elements (color).

Observing the nature of color we can see how perfectly it blends with light and gives an overall new look. Color being playful in itself gives more freedom, flexibility, and engagement to work with. While color is crucially considered the perception changes according to its tint, tone, and shade.

In the coming research paper, we will be focusing more on how color has an impact on toddler's emotions and behavioral patterns.

KEYWORDS: Emotions, Color, Toddlers, Color characteristics, Behavioral pattern and Environment.

INTRODUCTION

Color provokes emotions when they are revealed in their true nature. Each color has certain characteristics which are then reflected into the toddler's behavioral pattern.

Color and its characteristics-

- Red being part of the Primary color family it is perceived with emotions of Passion, Love, and Anger.
- Orange being the color of the warm color family represents with emotions of Energy and Happiness
- Yellow being the color of the primary color family shows the emotion of Happiness and Hope
- Green being the color of the cool color family it represents New Beginnings, Abundance, and Nature
- Blue being one of the primary colors Calm, Responsible, Sadness
- Purple inherited from the royal family it represents Creativity, Royalty, and Wealth
- White coming from a neutral family symbolizes Purity, Cleanliness, Virtue
- Pink Color is the universal color of love it represents friendship and affection.

Toddlers use color as a medium to connect with objects as well as materials in their environment. It helps them resonate with objects quicker hence color being the recall value for them. Once toddlers have a memory of any object it becomes easier for them to identify it, in any given environment. If toddlers use more than one of his/her sensory organs to understand the object, it becomes a long-term memory for them. Take the example of apples, if we let them touch and eat instead of just showing. Describing further in terms of color (red), it will be easier for them to memorize rather than just the image of apples.

Toddlers tend to identify objects either by their special features or their color. Color plays a vital role in a toddler's mood swings, emotions, and feelings. Along with their perceiving nature, either positively or negatively affecting their thought process. Once toddlers have a memory of an object it becomes easier for them to identify it in any given environment. Toys are a necessary part of a toddler's life. They are deeply attached to their toys. Considering their age factor, they are still protective and affectionate with their toys, parents, and things. Using the appropriate colors in their essentials (plates, toys, etc.) can give a beneficial outcome, making them engaged with it for a longer period, resulting in increased attention span. Using appealing colors for rides, swings, etc. in the playground will result in more pleasant moments for toddlers.

Value, chroma, and hue might be supportive in terms of the prediction of a young child's discrimination ability. Even after using the appropriate color schemes, there seems to be something missing. The source of light on the object affects the perception of color. Toddlers are attracted towards bright and flashy colors. We can observe that the toddler products have the majority of those colors respectively. Pop-ups in contrasting colors are easy to memorize.

Color holds the importance in communication, giving it a symbolic representation. Implication of color for educational purposes which will be truly focused on color and communication. If we take an example for preschoolers, where the pre-school can conduct some sessions having them all introduced to color while using everyday objects like fruit which it will be explained and make them recognize via their color characteristics.

By applying this approach there can be a development in understanding of the color quickly and opening more ways of communication.

Picture books have strong narrative illustrations which are essential for understanding the story. It is seen that primary and secondary colors are easily perceived so the illustrations have chosen colors. It could help in improving the cognitive and emotional development of a toddler.

We can place color in a structured manner that will create a positive influence on toddlers' minds, considering the fact that they have a certain connection towards their things (pillows, plates, water bottles). To mention that the majority of their essentials are either of their favorite color or of their favorite character.

From the observation, we can remark that mild/light/soft/tender color creates a sense of calmness, but seeing those colors again and again in a closed space might become boring for the toddler. Dark/strong colors give a sense of stability, whereas bright colors display joyous emotions. The change of color (scheme) in the environment affects behavioral patterns. Color schemes can be helpful while selecting a color for any object or room in a toddler's environment.

The human brain works in such a way that even if there is more than one color, the flashy color is perceived first, and while describing it is done by the prominent color.

If we take examples for a particular country or culture then we can observe how the color of that culture blends with the color of their surroundings. It will have emotional connectivity towards those colors instead of their different characteristics.

Toddlers often seem very particular about their preferences and throw a lot of tantrums. This is often taken as a negative expression as they can't express their needs properly to others, especially parents. They have their own way of expressing emotions, sometimes they will cry, shout or they might point out what they need. There are high chance that toddlers will eat the given food if it is made tempting compared to the usual bland food.

For example, we can add a twist in the usual white-colored rice by simply making it yellow in color, so that it will look more appealing. Adding this twist might take their attention and cheer them up. It is observed that toddlers might reject the food if they don't like the texture of that particular food so in this case vivid colors can be inculcated in the food to make it visually appealing for them.

Food being an integral part of our life consists of many food items with varied colors. Indian food is full of bright colors, such as yellow dal, green leafy vegetables, red pickles, white rice making the food journey exciting.

LITERATURE REVIEW

There are three light wavelengths short, medium, and long. The amount of light processed by the brain and eye could influence as well as trigger the toddler's behavioral and psychological patterns. We could see that light first attacks the brain leading to an instant psychological reaction and memory of it. It may point out changes in color preference as per the capacity of the eyes and brain to perceive light. Even if the wavelengths.

It can be seen that warm colors like red, yellow, and orange ignite a spark in a toddler's brain and make them active while cool colors like blue, and green keep them engaged for a longer duration of time. In a way, specific colors could be used for the required activity of toddlers. Like - Designing a play area or their bedroom. Possessing the knowledge of color effects on toddlers might help in increasing their attentiveness or duration of engagement. It is seen that color improves cooperation and coordination in toddlers.

Toddlers respond to colors in two different ways - either physiologically or psychologically. Physiological reactions involve changes in the body, such as eye comfort or discomfort, variations in blood pressure, and stress levels. Psychological reactions cause changes in mood and attentiveness.

We often observe two behavioral tendencies in toddlers: active and passive. As we know color preferences may vary among individuals, it's interesting to observe that active toddlers often lean toward cool colors. Their energy and enthusiasm seem to lead them to seek a more soothing and calm environment rather than one that is overly attractive or eye-catching.

In passive toddlers, they tend to be reserved and quiet in nature. There is often an inclination towards warm colors, as they seem to find the feelings of warmth and security that a palette of warm colors can create, giving a sense of comfort and safety in their surroundings.

While considering these warm and cool colors the most crucial part is purity and combination of the hue. The characteristics of the color including its tint, tone, and shade are vital as they influence toddlers' minds.

It is said that mild colors should be used for a toddler's environment but deciding the right amount is very critical. Using excessive amounts of mild color might have an adverse impact on toddlers' minds, as it can be dull in nature so being in the same environment for a longer duration can make one feel sad, and numb and kill its enthusiasm.

It could be beneficial for a toddler if they are not exposed to excessive colors or patterns at once, as this could lead to confusion.

Integrating gentle patterns and textures in a toddler's environment might help them familiarize themselves with the surroundings and encourage their sensory development.

CONCLUSION

We can conclude that colors have both positive and negative influence on toddlers' emotions as well as their behavioral patterns. Adding positive (bright) colors to a toddler's daily activities will increase their overall productivity.

We have seen other factors affecting the nature of color and placement of it.

Color becomes a means of learning and communicating new things for toddlers giving them more flexibility with words and languages. According to human behavior, we tend to remember it with their characteristics. Similarly for toddlers, if we use colors as a medium to remember things, it can lead to their cognitive development.

FUTURE IMPLICATIONS

- Pre-schools can conduct sessions based on color and communication.
- Redefining the toddler's environment for the understanding of tint, tone, and shade.
- The color palette of toddlers affects their eating habits.
- How culture and its color influence a toddler's emotions.
- Color schemes can be helpful while selecting a color for any object or room in a toddler's environment.

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